

The caption to Figure 7 published in ZooNova 20 by Whittington & Beuk (2022) was inadvertently transposed with that of Figure 5 and included a typo, which are corrected here.

Figure 7. Degree of colour variation in adult Lonchopteridae represented on Plate LXVIII (=68) of Meigen's unpublished volume (see Morge 1975). The names assigned to these figures by Meigen in the captions to figures (p.18) and the alphabetical list (p.89) are inserted, those for figures 3 and 8 being inconsistently given by Meigen (both names are provided here). Only *L. tristis* and *L. lutea* remain as valid names. Of the remainder, all are junior synonyms of *L. lutea*, except 3. *L. apicalis/L. lacustris* and *L. rivalis* (which are junior synonyms of *L. bifurcata*).